

IMAGINE-B5G

Vertical Use Cases, Facilities and Selected Projects of the First Open-Call

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Abstract—IMAGINE-B5G (Advanced 5G Open Platform for Large Scale Trials and Pilots across Europe) is an SNS Phase-1 Stream-D project which aims to implement an advanced and easily accessible end-to-end (E2E) B5G platform for large-scale trials and pilots providing a set of B5G applications, enabled by the integration of advanced 5G disrupting technologies. In this paper, we present the seven main vertical use cases targeted in IMAGINE-B5G along the four advanced 5G experimental facilities located in Norway, Spain, France, and Portugal. In addition, the onboarding of third parties (such as SMEs, industry, and researchers) for both vertical experiments and platform extensions through open calls is part of the IMAGINE-B5G road map. To that extent, we provide an overview of the 15 projects that were chosen for financing in the first open-call.

Keywords — *Beyond 5G; pilots; trials; verticals; facilities;*

I. INTRODUCTION

The IMAGINE-B5G project aims to build an advanced, easy-to-access, secure, and programmable end-to-end (E2E) beyond 5G (B5G) platform to fill in the gap between the B5G market expectations and the capabilities of existing 5G-PPP infrastructure projects. The platform is composed of four advanced 5G experimental facilities, located in Norway, Spain, France, and Portugal, respectively. It serves the use cases in vertical industries of media, Public Protection and Disaster Recovery (PPDR), eHealth, agriculture & forestry, education, transportation & logistics, and Industry 4.0. With well-defined APIs, these use cases can onboard their applications and validate their specific KPIs and KVIIs.

Although all facilities provide 5G and B5G services, they each use different technology solutions, which lead to different ways of building, deploying, managing, and operating their 5G networks. For example, the French and Portuguese facilities are specialized in open-source solutions for trials of advanced features while other facilities provide near-commercial solutions for large-scale trials. Such diversity creates the flexibility and agility to support different experimenters, ranging from academic and research-oriented groups to industrial and development-oriented professionals.

To support the ever-growing demands from these vertical use cases, the IMAGINE-B5G platform is continuously evolving, associated with three platform releases, each of which will be accompanied by the addition of advanced 5G and B5G features. The platform evolution is also linked to three open calls

which target attracting external partners who will contribute to the platform extensions and co-creation of innovative use cases. It is expected that around 50 projects will be funded across the three open calls.

The outcome of the vertical experiments running on the IMAGINE-B5G platform will help the project to gain a better understanding of the social implications of the proposed B5G solutions. As a result, society will be able to optimize the strategy and roadmap of adopting B5G into business and society development.

II. IMAGINE-B5G VERTICAL USE CASES

Advanced 5G networks are significantly changing the landscape of various industries and verticals, enabling the creation of efficient and scalable new solutions and products. This is attributed to the potential of B5G networks to offer an array of enhanced capabilities and experiences surpassing current network technologies. Moreover, B5G networks will also generate novel business prospects, fostering the emergence of new services and applications across diverse sectors such as smart cities, IoT, and edge computing.

The conception of IMAGINE-B5G facilities underscores the availability of resources and a conducive ecosystem for experimenting with innovative advanced 5G features within B5G use cases. While additional verticals and use cases may be explored, mainly as a result of the open calls processes, the project primarily targets the following sectors:

i. Public Protection and Disaster Relief (PPDR)

PPDR encompasses activities aimed at safeguarding the public and responding to emergencies. In the IMAGINE-B5G project, PPDR efforts will involve disaster response, evacuation planning, search and rescue operations, and providing critical services. Advanced technologies like communication systems, early warning systems, and remote sensing often play a vital role in supporting these activities. The overarching goal of PPDR is to mitigate the impact of disasters on communities and individuals, ensuring swift and effective protection and assistance.

ii. Media

The media industry creates diverse multimedia content for entertainment, gaming, sports, and more. Traditionally, 2D video and stereo audio have been standard, but there's a growing demand for immersive content supported by innovative technologies like haptics, holograms, and surrounding audio.

This shift requires new network functionalities to both distribute and produce this content. In IMAGINE-B5G, media activities will focus on studying how immersive technologies such as XR, haptics, and holograms are becoming essential for the future media ecosystem.

iii. Transportation and Logistics

The transportation and logistics sector focuses on managing transportation workflows. Advanced location features can enhance industrial operations, facilitating flexible asset tracking, route optimization, and the deployment of Automatic Guided Vehicles (AGVs). Transportation scenarios extend beyond logistics and encompass diverse communication needs, requiring robust networking systems. In IMAGINE-B5G, transportation and logistics activities will explore autonomous driving positioning and the integration of AGVs into various stages of industrial production processes.

iv. Industry 4.0

The industry 4.0 sector focuses on manufacturing goods using equipment, machines, and tools. Future industries aim to leverage emerging technologies to enhance production processes, making them smarter, connected, and automated. This evolution promises increased efficiency, cost-effectiveness, speed, and sustainability in production. IMAGINE-B5G is dedicated to advancing smart automation and optimization within production processes.

v. Education

The education sector focuses on imparting knowledge, with evolving practices incorporating information technologies. Remote teaching is crucial for accommodating students unable to attend physically, while improving knowledge transmission methods to enhance understanding and retention is essential. In IMAGINE-B5G, exploration of technologies such as immersive telepresence, holograms, XR, and haptics will be key in advancing education.

vi. Smart Agriculture and Forestry

The smart agriculture and forestry sector focuses on modernizing farming and cultivation practices. Digitalization and automation are reshaping agriculture, with autonomous vehicles already in use for various tasks. Further enhancements are anticipated with the integration of advanced technologies like advanced mobile networks, imaging techniques, AI, ML, and immersive communications. IMAGINE-B5G will demonstrate how these technologies can revolutionize tasks such as infestation detection, fertilization, field analysis via imaging, teleoperation of machinery, surveillance, and weather prediction in agriculture and forestry.

vii. eHealth

The eHealth sector focuses on leveraging technology to enhance healthcare services. Future healthcare systems are expected to offer remote assistance through technologies like remote monitoring devices, immersive experiences for cognitive rehabilitation, and robots for home care. These systems require precise motion control, low latency, and seamless interfaces between doctors and patients to ensure safe and effective medical activities. IMAGINE-B5G aims to explore how these

technologies can be integrated into healthcare to provide timely and natural medical care.

III. IMAGINE-B5G FACILITIES

The IMAGINE-B5G platform brings together four advanced 5G experimental facilities, located in Norway, Spain, France, and Portugal dedicated for large-scale trials and pilots. Collectively, these facilities will support several B5G use cases, described in Section II, enabled by the integration of a diverse set of advanced 5G technologies. In this regard, the infrastructure of the facilities in Norway, Spain and Portugal are based on industry equipment, with some components being open-source. On the contrary, the French facility relies on a completely open-source end-to-end 5G implementation. Next, we provide a brief description of each of the four facilities.

Norway Facility

The Norwegian facility, led by Telenor, is closer to the commercial rollout and operations compared to other experimental testbeds. The core and access networks are built from either commercial or near-commercial solutions, which are relatively stable and scalable compared to open-source solutions but also give the leverage of exploring new and advanced features. The facility bridges the gap between the commercial 5G networks and the pure open 5G testbeds, allowing to experiment with more innovative solutions and transfer them to the commercial operations and productions more quickly. The facility includes a central site in Fornebu as well as several edge and Radio Access Network (RAN) sites across Norway, which are interconnected by Telenor Norway's commercial transport network.

One such notable site is the Sustainable Immersive Networking Laboratory (SIN-Lab). SIN-Lab is located at University of Oslo (UiO) and it is considered a playground for immersive networking research that focuses on providing a true sensation of presence in the remote location through haptic interaction. SIN-Lab is equipped with a wide range of state-of-the-art multimedia (e.g., cameras, LIDARs, headsets, glasses VR) and haptic devices (e.g., haptic gloves, in-air touch feedback, and haptic body suit) to support a variety of immersive applications.

The Norwegian facility also has the possibility to deploy autonomous 5G networks in remote areas using Network on Wheels (NoWs), this solution allows the deployment of full 5G SA networks on demand in remote areas with no coverage with guaranteed Quality of Service (QoS). The 5G Core (5GC) network solution adopted is compliant with 3GPP Rel16 5GC service-based architecture and contains all the fundamental independent, reusable, and independent 5GC network functions. The facility constitutes multiple vendors regarding RAN equipment, mainly Huawei and Ericsson. The virtualization platform adopted in the Norwegian facility is based on Red Hat OpenShift Container Platform (OCP) which can host and manage both VM-based and container-based network functions, as well as network/vertical applications. The Norwegian facility has a full-stack orchestration, based on the Nokia Orchestration Center (NorC), allowing the automation of the deployment of infrastructure, network services, and network slices. Nokia Cloud Operation Manager (NCOM) is used to manage the life

cycle of Cloud-Native Network Functions (CNFs) including the 5GC functions and applications.

Spanish Facility

The Spanish facility comprises four sites: UPV campus and the port in Valencia, a rural site in Soria, and an experimental laboratory in Madrid. These sites are formed by different Radio Access Technologies (RAT) and independent 5GC; it will be evolved during the project to obtain an interconnected and distributed infrastructure.

The UPV campus is formed by two cells, connected to the same 5GC, providing coverage around the campus (~0.1km²), and located on the roof of two different UPV buildings. The cells have the same radio configuration, operating on the same frequency band (n258, n40, and B7), enabling the handover between them. The scenario has multiple environments for trials and use cases, such as sports fields, educational classes, gardens, and roads. Moreover, the UPV site has an immersive laboratory with tactile and holographic equipment, with 5G Standalone (SA) coverage in n78 band. Also, to perform trials and use cases where there is no 5G coverage, UPV has a portable base station working in the n40 band.

The Valencia port has a millimeter Wave (mmW) 5G Non-Standalone (NSA) network providing coverage next to cruise berths, enabling it to perform some use cases and trials in a port environment. The network is interconnected with the experimental laboratory in Madrid, where several KPIs from the core and energy data are stored and processed.

The rural site in Soria covers an agriculture area and it aims to trial a zero emissions solution for monitoring and surveying agricultural sites, being fully powered by renewable energy, and providing connectivity to different IoT devices and hardware to perform computation at the edge.

The experimental laboratory located at Nokia's premises offers an excellent environment to test various network solutions, configures and manages all sites, and provides a field trial with different technologies and frequency bands.

The Spanish facility will have different 5GC, allowing for more extensive testing, with each core having different features. The available 5GC include Open5GS, CumuCore, open5Gcore and Amarisoft Callbox. The facility uses Nokia RAN equipment such as the AirScale Micro RRH 4T4R (AHHA – 474147A). The Spanish facility has an outpost server, which is a fully-managed service that will extend AWS infrastructure, services, Application Programming Interfaces (API), and tools to the facility through the on-premises server. It allows running AWS services locally, while seamlessly connecting to other AWS regions. This allows moving workloads between the edge and the cloud seamlessly. Regarding Network and Service orchestration, Network as Code (NaC) and CAPIF APIs make the selection and activate the appropriate hardware and software resources to guarantee the quality of service which is needed in every individual scenario.

French Facility

The French facility, located at EURECOM, provides experimental 5G services including eMBB, URLLC, and mMTC. Based on fully open-source tools and open architecture design, it provides the means to on-board new network functions, services and vertical applications to the running 5G

infrastructure and testing them in both a controlled laboratory setting and in a deployed live network.

The core network, based on 3GPP Rel16, is fully open and configurable within the limitations of the OAI implementation. All the CNFs can be deployed as docker containers either using docker, Kubernetes or OpenShift. Each NF is initially configured using configuration files and can be configured during run time using dedicated APIs. The French facility RAN platform is splitted into Distributed Unit (DU), Centralized Unit (CU) and RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC). The DU/CU are based on OAI for both indoor and outdoor deployments. OAI DU supports O-RAN split 7.2 with commercial Radio Units (RU) such as LiteON and VVDN; and split 8 with USRPs. The RIC is based on FlexRIC which provides a Software Development Kit (SDK) to develop xApps using the O-RAN compliant KPM, RC and custom Service Models (SM). All the RAN components are based on containers and can run on the top of Kubernetes or OpenShift clusters. Moreover, the 5GC functions, CU, DU, RIC, xApps and vertical applications can be deployed using a home made service orchestrator. The latter manages the life cycle of the different CNFs and monitors their KPIs and logs.

Portuguese Facility

The Portuguese site features a platform that exploits a rich set of capabilities and characteristics that go beyond the mere aggregation of equipment. The overall infrastructure features both research and commercial-graded solutions and open labs to provide a real-life city-wide environment for developing, integrating, and testing novel solutions for 5G and beyond technologies.

The infrastructure is geographically distributed across the city area and encompasses various indoor and outdoor 5G New Radio (NR) deployments supported with different Core and Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) solutions. The available 5G cores include Raemis, Open5GCore, Open5GS and Huawei. The RAN is deployed in two domains. The first one, connected to Huawei 5GC, and based on Huawei equipment is deployed in three main sites: (i) ITAV (ii) university electrical substations 400m away from ITAV; (iii) Industrial location 6km away from ITAV. While the second domain follows O-RAN architecture where the DU and CU components are based on ASOCS CYRUS 2.0, and the RU comes from ASOCS and Altice Labs. The facility provides edge computing capabilities, where latency-sensitive applications, such as Extended Reality (XR) can be deployed to take advantage of low latency conditions and improved bandwidth efficiency. Three edge computing platforms are currently available: (i) Intel Open Network Edge Services Software (OpenNESS); (ii) EdgeGallery; (iii) Huawei MEC platform. The different resources (e.g., RAN, Core, Edge, Cloud) are managed and operated by different solutions. On one hand, the commercial-graded 5G infrastructure (i.e., 5GC, 5G NR, and 5G MEC) is monitored by a Huawei eSight platform as well as a Mobile Automation Engine (MAE) solution. The Management and Orchestration (MANO) role, currently played by SONATA and OpenSource MANO (OSM), is responsible for receiving requests from other systems (e.g., service orchestration, OSS/BSS, portals) and orderly executing them on top of the available Network Functions Virtualization Infrastructure (NFVI).

IV. OPEN-CALL 1 PLATFORM EXTENSIONS PROPOSALS

During the first Open Call, IMAGINE-B5G received 20 Platform Extension proposals, 5 of them were selected for funding. Next, we provide a high-level overview of each project's objectives and expected contributions.

Norway Facility

5G-and-beyond Network Extensions towards Public neTwork integrated non-pUblc NETworks (5G-NEPTUNE)

5G-NEPTUNE will extend the IMAGINE-B5G Norwegian facility by providing Telenor with a new non-public 5GC instance for Public Network Integrated Non-Public Network (PNINPN) experimentation, and by equipping NoW 1 with an upgraded commercial-grade 5GC. The latter will include an IP Multimedia Subsystem (IMS), supporting services such as Voice over New Radio (VoNR), Voice over IP (VoIP), and Mission Critical Services (MCX). Later, 5G-NEPTUNE will work on the design of solutions to integrate NoW 1 with Telenor's Experimentation Platform towards a Public Network Integrated NoW (PNI-NoW). 5G-NEPTUNE will include testing campaigns and an analysis of the obtained results, in collaboration with IMAGINEB5G's partners and vertical stakeholders, and with a focus on use case scenarios relevant to them. This project is relevant for IMAGINE-B5G's vertical use cases PPDR, Media, Smart Agriculture and Forestry, and e-Health.

Spanish Facility

Bidirectional education system based on holographic cabins through 5g Networks (BiNetHol)

BiNetHol aims to validate the use of holographic cabins in the educational field, employing 5G networks for unidirectional and bidirectional signal transmission. The core objective is to grant remote individuals a learning experience equivalent to being physically present with the instructor. Likewise, these geographically separated participants should interact as if sharing the same space, posing queries and offering real-time commentary. This two-way interaction ensures seamless engagement, akin to proximity. Through bidirectional holography, both locations provide precise spatial awareness of participants, including their movements. Each attendee can observe the relative positions of others and adapt their focus based on context—be it hands, faces, or objects. This project is relevant for IMAGINE-B5G's vertical use cases Media and Education.

French Facility

i. F-EXTENSION: Extension of the IMAGINE-B5G French platform

F-EXTENSION goes beyond the state-of-the-art 3GPP Rel-16 features, adding three extensions to the IMAGINE-B5G French facility. In particular, F-EXTENSION aims to i) implement a 3GPP-compliant Two-step RACH feature to support Short Data Transmission (SDT), ii) propose and implement algorithms to enable Joint Communication and Sensing (JCAS) using OAI and Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS), and iii) develop an OEM for OAI 5G CN that

allows deploying, configuring, and terminating CN instances via a graphical web interface. This extension, in particular, will also allow the visualisation of different events exposed by the CN. This project is relevant for IMAGINE-B5G's vertical use cases Transport and Logistics and Industry 4.0.

ii. CAMARA API: Extending IMAGINE-B5G framework & facilities

CAMARA API focuses on improving the IMAGINE-B5G French platform by integrating and developing the CAMARA API seamlessly. The IMAGINE-B5G platform forms the base, and by integrating the CAMARA API, our goal is to expand its capabilities. This integration will lead to a more powerful and adaptable system, enhancing performance and usability within the context of 5G communication technologies. This extension is designed to leverage the framework's existing capabilities while introducing advanced functionalities that are essential for the evolving needs of B5G networks and their users. The primary goal of this extension is to enhance the efficiency and capabilities of the B5G framework, user experience, and overall performance, without adding unnecessary complexity to the system. The CAMARA API aims to enhance the performance of the IMAGINE-B5G platform in pivotal domains including enhanced localization of devices and resources, device identification retrieval, status updates, and resource availability and allocation. By bolstering these areas, the API endeavors to create a platform that is more robust, agile, and user-centric, catering to application developers engaging with the IMAGINE-B5G ecosystem.

Portuguese Facility

Imagine B-5G srsRAN Platform Extension (SRS-B5G)

SRS-B5G will extend IMAGINE-B5G facilities in Portugal with a complete multicell Open RAN deployment based on the srsRAN solution. This deployment will further be enhanced with 5G RAN positioning features including NRPPa positioning protocol and 5G Positioning Reference Signals (NR PRS). In summary, the key objectives of the SRS-B5G project are to i) expand the IMAGINE-B5G Portuguese facility with an Open RAN deployment based on srsRAN, ii) enhance this Open RAN deployment with 5G RAN positioning features, and iii) showcase flexible deployable RAN solutions using srsRAN.

V. OPEN-CALL 1 VERTICAL EXPERIMENTS PROPOSALS
IMAGINE-B5G received 44 Vertical Experiment proposals, 10 of them were selected for funding. In the following, we provide a high-level overview of each project's objectives and expected contributions. In addition, Table 1 provides a mapping of the IMAGINE-B5G use cases targeted with each project.

Norway Facility

i. 5G-enabled AI gloves as Industry 4.0 IoT sensor of human activity (ALMA)

ALMA aims to integrate the solution for the training of blue-collar workers in a realistic Industry 4.0 environment. It should contain a 5G network and on-premise cloud. This will validate the infrastructure readiness and help Mimetik in business with customers using similar networks. For this purpose, Mimetik intends to use the fully functional prototype that is already

available and currently equipped with wifi. During the project, Mimetik will add a 5G capability and test the full system with resources available at the IMAGINE-B5G facility in Norway.

ii. Leveraging Edge Optical Sensing for Emergency Diagnostics (LEOSED)

Integration optical wireless sensing of pulse and blood oxygen saturation (OWSPOS) in B5G/6G edge can support swift critical patient diagnosis and monitoring in the health sector. OWSPOS achieves this goal through contact-less and automated measurement of vitals, and is aimed at two aspects. First, it can reduce the risk of introducing new patients to a wrong triage level. Second, the implementation can be used in long term patient monitoring in conjunction with current monitoring devices, or as a standalone implementation. The main goal of LEOSED is to test the feasibility of OWSPOS as a key B5G/6G eHealth vertical application and perform experiments to understand its communication and computation requirements.

iii. Artificial Intelligence for Forest Surveillance (AI4FS)

AI4FS aims to design a UC that promotes an advanced forestry monitoring methodology. More specifically, tree counting, tree health and optimized forest monitoring will be implemented through aerial and ground sensors. For this reason, ground sensors will measure environmental variables and directly transmit those to the edge server. Additionally, a UAV equipped with a multispectral and RGB cameras will provide real time video streaming to the same edge server where the CV models will be deployed

Spanish Facility

i. Agro-4.0 based on 5G (AGRO4-5G)

Precision agriculture allows to anticipate crop management decisions and base them on measurable and objective information, avoiding making decisions based solely on intuition. AGRO4-5G provides remote information about the status of the crop, so the producer knows how the production is proceeding. In addition, it provides context to data through the combination of different data sources, e.g., from sensors and stations installed on a plot, with data from climatic stations, soil analysis data and satellite images. This data is processed together to provide it with a context and turn it into useful information. During the AGRO4-5G will provide, install, and maintain 8 ground stations to get data related with roots activity, humidity and nutrition; and 4 weather stations to get data related to the more useful weather parameters in terms of agriculture management. The aim of the test is to verify the feasibility of using 5G technologies in agriculture IoT deployments. There are many aspects that are relevant and will be tested like energy consumption in each station (communication systems and processing unit), coverage, network performance and management capabilities.

ii. Advanced Drone-Assisted Port Technology with Augmented Reality and 5G Communications (ADAPT-AR5G)

ADAPT-AR5G project aims at revolutionizing port surveillance through the integration of our technologies, including drones, augmented reality (AR) devices, and 5G communications. The primary objective of this experiment is to

develop an advanced and integrated surveillance system, enabling real-time monitoring of port accesses, restricted areas, and potential security threats. The experiment holds significant promise in enhancing port security, streamlining access monitoring, and optimizing operational efficiency at the esteemed Port of Valencia.

iii. eDgE platforM for dynamiC xR applicATIOnS (DEMOCRATS)

Extended Reality applications with a new level of immersive interactions enable a new generation of applications in many fields. However, the required quality of user experience poses several challenges. DEMOCRATS will deploy a novel edge/cloud-based XR platform to the Imagine B5G infrastructure, where resource-intensive tasks are offloaded to the edge, while delay-critical tasks are executed on the head-mounted display. The targeted use case is a multi-player car soccer game, where small remote-controlled cars, detected/tracked in real-time, play with a virtual ball. Experiments will be conducted with the demo application and user experience will be analyzed in different network scenarios.

French Facility

i. Enabling Proximity Services: A Server-based practical deployment (ProSe-Serv)

Proximity Services (ProSe) in 3GPP enable direct device-to-device communication based on proximity. Primarily serving public safety and commercial discovery, ProSe utilizes proximity awareness to actively/passively seek value in physical/virtual proximity. While currently limited on mobile phones, ProSe is crucial during network downtime or out-of-coverage scenarios. Despite being defined in 3GPP, it's not yet available in telecom equipment. ProSe-Serv suggests deploying ProSe, independent of 5G implementation, leveraging existing 5G and WiFi Direct capabilities. This solution, aligned with Open5GLab and O-RAN, aligns with IMAGINE-B5G goals, offering flexibility and programmability within a disaggregated RAN framework.

Portuguese Facility

i. Drone Care Angel (DCA): Mobile health monitoring as a service enabled by beyond 5G

DCA aims to validate beyond 5G features for a Drone Care Angel service, focusing on the real-time health monitoring of individuals on the move. This novel service will be enabled by the transmission of a richer amount of information collected and aggregated by a drone, while tracking a person, with the support of additional data collected via available Internet of Things devices (e.g., video, health sensor data). Upon identification of health-impacting incidents (e.g., heart attack, robbery attempts), a top data tier is activated to enable a 360° perception of the scene via the increase of volume, complexity and/or richness of transmitted data (e.g., additional data sources, increased video resolution or derived Augmented Reality elements).

ii. Ultra Low Latency M2M communications for 5G enabled Fabrication Systems (ULTRA-FAB5G)

The primary objective of the ULTRA-FAB5G is to assess and validate a comprehensive shopfloor-centric private 5G

communications network layer by implementing a dependable and secure low-latency 5G communication framework that can effectively replace legacy wired cable systems-based communication networks in the shopfloor. The solution will be part of the Portuguese facility.

iii. Situational Awareness Framework Enabling Robust Emergency Response for Urban Flood Warnings (SAFER-FLOW)

SAFER-FLOW will enhance PPDR by integrating advanced beyond 5G technologies and applications for handling demanding flooding scenarios. The experiment will use the city of Aveiro, Portugal, as the integration and demonstration testbed, combining the availability of the IMAGINE-B5G Portuguese facility site with the vulnerability to complex urban flooding scenarios that characterise the city of Aveiro. Overall, the proposed experiment will showcase the effectiveness of OneSource’s SAFER-FLOW platform and validate the IMAGINE-B5G infrastructure for disaster management events.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has presented the 15 projects (4 Platform Extensions and 11 Vertical Experiments) selected for funding the first open-call of the SNS Phase-I Stream D project IMAGINE-B5G, with an approximate budget of 1.9 M€.

The second open-call is currently open, with 2M€ funding for Platform Extensions and Vertical Experiments of 12 months (expected starting date October 2024). In 2025 there will be a third and final open-call for Vertical Experiments lasting 6 months.

Table 1. Mapping of the Vertical Experiments project with IMAGINE-B5G use cases.

	NO			SP			FR	PO		
	i	ii	iii	i	ii	iii	i	i	ii	iii
PPDR					X			X		X
Media					X	X	X			
Education	X					X				
Smart Agriculture & Forestry			X	X						
eHealth		X						X		
Transport & Logistics										
Industry 4.0	X				X				X	

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